

Local vertical stresses in web plates of crane runway girders near transverse stiffeners

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ABSTRACT

Crane runway girders in industrial buildings are typically subjected to high fatigue relevant stresses during crane operation. Due to the concentrated wheel load introduction via the crane wheels on the crane rails, high local vertical stresses occur on the upper edge of the web plate of the crane runway girder. These local stresses are decisive for the fatigue design of the welded connection between the web and the upper flange. Generally, transverse stiffeners are situated at regular distances to improve the buckling resistance and to limit rotation of the top flange due to eccentric introduction of the vertical wheel loads. The stiffeners are usually welded to the web plate and the top flange, in most cases with cut-outs near the web to flange junctions. These welds at the transverse stiffeners represent additional fatigue-relevant notch details. Design rules in prEN 1993-6 (1) give no clear information about the intensity of the local stresses at these notch details. Within this paper, a numerical parametric study is carried out to investigate the local dominating vertical stresses near transverse stiffeners. These stresses are compared to the vertical stresses on the upper edge of the web plate (at positions without transverse stiffeners). The latter can be calculated with formulae from prEN 1993-6 (1). Furthermore, the additional notch details in the region of the transverse stiffeners are classified with the nominal stress fatigue resistances in prEN 1993-1-9 (2). The fatigue verification of the additional notch details (with their actual stresses) in relation to the detail of the welded web-flange-connection allows an assessment of the additional notch details (relevant for fatigue design or not).

Keywords: crane runway girder, transverse stiffener, local stresses

1 INTRODUCTION

Overhead bridge cranes are used in almost every industrial building to lift and carry heavy weights. The main crane runway girders on which the bridge crane is travelling are vulnerable to fatigue damage due to high wheel loads and a high number of load cycles. For heavy crane operations the crane runway girder is often constructed as welded I-section. A special characteristic of this crane runway girder is that the rail, on which the bridge crane travels, is bedded direct on the top flange. Since the wheel loads are introduced concentrated in the girder, high local vertical stresses σ_z occur on the top edge of the web plate in addition to the global longitudinal bending stresses σ_x . However, this local stresses in combination with the constructional detail of the welded connection between web plate and top flange often becomes decisive for the fatigue assessment of the crane runway girder. The fatigue resistance of the welded connection between the web plate and the top flange can be found in prEN 1993-1-9 (2).

Formulae to calculate the magnitude of the local vertical stresses, only in regions between transverse stiffeners, are given in prEN 1993-6 (1). The analytic derivation of the membrane stresses in the web plate was first published in (3). For heavy crane operation an eccentric introduction of the wheel load, which results in an additional transverse bending of the web plate,

has to be considered in the fatigue assessment. The formulae to determine the transverse bending stress component in the web plate was derived in (4) and (5).

To prevent the slender web plates of the crane runway girder from buckling, and to support the top flange against rotation due to eccentric wheel load introduction transverse stiffeners are situated at regular distances. Since the transverse stiffeners are welded to the crane runway girder, additional fatigue relevant constructional details are generated in the regions affected by the local stresses. The standard constructional detail of transverse stiffeners in main girders with welded I-sections has a cut-out in the corners so that the weld between the web plate and the flange can be passed through.

Fig. 1a shows a schematic illustration of a crane runway girder with a crossing crane. When the wheel load is introduced between two transverse stiffeners, local vertical stresses occur in the welded connection between top flange and web plate (detail 1). The fatigue assessment for this detail can be done with the calculated stresses from (1) and the fatigue resistance from (2). However, local stresses are introduced also for wheel load introduction direct above the transverse stiffener. For the local stresses three relevant notch details can be identified in this area for typical constructions (see *Fig. 1b*). The connection between web and flange (detail 1) is also present in this area, since in most practical cases the transvers stiffener has a cut-out. At the lower end of the cut-out where the transverse stiffener is welded to the web plate there is also a relevant notch detail claimed by vertical stresses (detail 2). If the transvers stiffener is welded to the top flange a third relevant constructional detail occur in this area, called detail 3 in *Fig. 1b*. The fatigue resistance of the constructional details can be found in (2). However, there is no information about the intensity of the vertical stresses in these areas in current design rules. A proposal for determining the stresses was given in (6), but with the restriction that the transverse stiffener has no cut-out.

Fig. 1. a) crane positions in longitudinal direction between two transverse stiffeners and directly above the transverse stiffener; b) Decisive constructional details at position of the transverse stiffener

This paper presents a numerical parametric study which investigates the local stresses due to wheel loading at details 1, to 3 in the region of transverse stiffeners. Influences of different cross sections of crane runway girders are highlighted. Finally, a fatigue assessment of details 1 to 3 with transverse stiffener is presented in section 4, by comparing the utilization factors of the fatigue verification with those of the welded web-flange connection without transverse stiffener.

2 NUMERIC PARAMETRIC STUDY

The intensity of the local vertical stresses at position of the critical points near the transverse stiffener (see *Fig. 1*) are investigated with a numeric parametric study. The parametric study was conducted in (7), and the main results are presented within this paper in section 3.

2.1 Finite Element Model

The parametric study was carried out with the finite element software Abaqus. A local model of a welded crane runway girder with I-section was prepared (see *Fig. 2*), since only the local vertical stresses near the transverse stiffener are evaluated. These local stresses are not influenced by global

bending behaviour of the girder. This form of a local model was also validated with laboratory test on a real crane runway girder in (8).

Fig. 2. a) Finite Element Model for the parametric study with symmetry plane at load introduction ($a=h_w$); b) connection area of the transverse stiffener with cope hole and result paths for determining the stresses at detail 1, 2 and 3

Fig. 2a shows the geometry and the mesh of the FE-model. In longitudinal direction, one web field between two transverse stiffeners was modelled. Symmetric results about the plane of load introduction (directly above the transverse stiffener) can be expected, so a symmetry boundary condition was used to reduce the number of elements. The load was applied in the symmetry plane in two steps. In the first step the vertical wheel load F_z was applied concentric to the web plate of the girder. In the second step an additional torsion Moment M_T was applied while the concentric load was maintained. The moment M_T was calculated with Eq. (1), based on the regulations in (1) for fatigue verification.

$$M_T = F_z \cdot \max\left(\frac{k}{4}; \frac{t_w}{2}\right) \quad (1)$$

where k is the width of the rail head and t_w is the web thickness of the crane runway girder.

This procedure of load application has the advantage that both, concentric loading, and eccentric loading can be done in one calculation.

The girder is supported vertically at position of the exterior stiffener and in transverse direction at both positions (also in the symmetry plane) of transverse stiffeners, see Fig. 2. The contact behaviour between the rail and the top flange of the girder is a rigid contact which allows the separation of the rail. Only the edges of the rail can transmit tensile stresses, to simulate the rail clamps. No elastomeric bearing pad is considered in the numeric calculations.

For the upper part of the girder and the transverse stiffener quadratic brick elements of type C3DR20 are used. For the lower half of the model linear elements of type C3DR8 are used. The outer transverse stiffener is modelled with shell elements (type S4R).

The locations of the result paths are shown in Fig. 2b. The local vertical stresses in the welded connection between the top flange and the web (detail 1) are evaluated 10 mm below the top flange (path 1-1 in Fig. 2b). For the welded connection between the transverse stiffener and the web, respectively the transverse stiffener and the flange, the vertical stresses are evaluated at path 2-2, at a distance of 10 mm above the bottom of the cut-out, and at path 3-3 directly below the top flange (see Fig. 2b).

2.2 Investigated geometry of crane runway girder and transverse stiffeners

To evaluate the local stress fields near the transverse stiffeners, 24 different FE-models were developed with varying geometry of the crane rail, the crane runway girder, and the transverse

stiffener. This specific selection of individual parameters allows to quantify the influence of these parameters on the relevant maximum local stresses at detail 1 to 3, shown in section 3. An overview of the presented FE-models is given in *Table 1*. Only the flange width and the overall width of the transverse stiffeners was kept constant with $b_f = 400$ mm and $b_s = 380$ mm, respectively.

Fig. 3 shows three different variants of cut-outs in the transverse stiffener to investigate the influence on the vertical stresses in the web plate as well as in the transverse stiffener. Variant v1 is a cut-out with triangular shape, variant v2 with circular shape and variant v3 is the same as variant v2 but with elongated cut-outs in vertical direction. The variation of the cut-out with different sizes r was done within the FE-models 1 to 6 with the rail type A 100 and models 17 to 19 with a rail type A 55 (see *Table 1*).

Fig. 3. a) Investigated types of cut-outs in the transverse stiffener

Furthermore, the thickness values of the crane runway girders flange t_f and web t_w have been varied as well as the thickness of the transverse stiffener t_s .

Table 1. Dimensions of the investigated FE-models

FE-model number	crane runway girder			transverse stiffener		FE-model number	crane runway girder			transverse stiffener	
	t_f	t_w	h_w	t_s	r (cut-out)		t_f	t_w	h_w	t_s	r (cut-out)
1	20	15	2000	10	45 (v1)	13	20	15	2000	13	65 (v2)
2	20	15	2000	10	45 (v2)	14	20	15	2000	15	65 (v2)
3	20	15	2000	10	45 (v3)	15	20	15	1000	10	65 (v2)
4	20	15	2000	10	65 (v2)	16	20	15	500	10	65 (v2)
5	20	15	2000	10	65 (v3)	17	20	15	2000	10	45 (v2)
6	20	15	2000	10	100 (v2)	18	20	15	2000	10	65 (v2)
7	30	15	2000	10	65 (v2)	19	20	15	2000	10	100 (v2)
8	40	15	2000	10	65 (v2)	20	30	15	2000	10	65 (v2)
9	45	15	2000	10	65 (v2)	21	40	15	2000	10	65 (v2)
10	20	10	2000	10	65 (v2)	22	20	20	2000	10	65 (v2)
11	20	13	2000	10	65 (v2)	23	20	15	2000	10	65 (v2)
12	20	20	2000	10	65 (v2)	24	20	15	2000	10	65(v2)

Note 1: all crane runway girders have dimensions of $b_f = 400$ mm, $b_s = 380$ mm and $a = h_w$

Note 2: models 1-16: crane rail A 100; models 17-22: crane rail A 55; model 23: crane rail A 75 and model 24 crane rail A 120

3 RESULTS OF THE PARAMETRIC STUDY

The vertical stresses in the web of the crane runway girder and the transverse stiffener were calculated for the 24 different configurations (see *Table 1*). For each model the local stresses are evaluated at the decisive notch details 1, 2 and 3 with the result paths from *Fig. 2b*. So, the influence of the geometry of the crane runway girder and transverse stiffeners on the local stresses can be investigated. The distributions of the local stresses in longitudinal direction of the web plate and in transverse direction of the transverse stiffener has been analysed as well as the magnitude of the maximum stress value direct below the load. Due to lack of space only the influence of the most significant parameters is shown within this paper.

3.1 Influence of different cut-outs in the transverse stiffeners

Fig. 4 shows the distribution of vertical stresses in the transverse stiffener and in the web of the crane runway girder for the three different variants of cut-outs in the stiffener (see Fig. 3). The stress distributions are plotted for a concentric introduced wheel load $F_z = 250$ kN on a crane rail A 100. The dimensions of the crane runway girder are the same for the models 1 to 5 (see Table 1).

Fig 4a shows the stress distribution in the **transverse** stiffener (result path 3-3 in Fig. 2). The value $y = 0$ is in the axis of the girder's web, therefore the end of the stress distribution differs for different sizes r of the cut-out. The stress distribution in longitudinal direction of the web plate is presented in Fig. 4b. In the left half of the diagram the vertical stresses near the top flange are plotted (result path 1-1 for detail 1) and in the right half the stresses are shown for the result path 2-2 (vertical stresses on the lower end of the cut-out, detail 2). The transverse stiffener and the load introduction are located at $x = 0$.

Fig. 4. Distribution of vertical stresses σ_z , a) in the transverse stiffener; b) in the web of the crane girder in longitudinal direction for detail 1 and 2, for FE-models 1 to 5 and for an applied concentric wheel load of $F_z = 250$ kN

The stress distributions in the transverse stiffener in Fig. 4a shows, that there is no significant influence of the cut-outs dimension r on the distribution of vertical stresses. The stresses are slightly higher for the cut-out with $r = 45$ mm ($\sigma_{\max} = -81.4$ N/mm²) because the end of the transverse stiffener is closer to the load application. The smallest compression stresses occur in the case of the triangular shaped cut-out ($r = 45_v1$), with $\sigma_{\max} = -60.6$ N/mm². The stress distribution in the web plate for detail 1 in Fig. 4b shows no influence of the triangular or the circular cut-out and the dimension r . For the stresses in the girder's web at detail 2 (lower edge of the cut-out) no influence can be reported for the triangular and the circular shape of the cut-out. The magnitude of the stresses is also in the same range as on the top of the web ($\sigma_{\max} = -64.3$ N/mm²). However, for the elongated cut-outs (variant v3) a significant reduction of the vertical compression stresses at detail 2 occurs ($\sigma_{\max} = -52.4$ N/mm² for $r = 45$ mm and $\sigma_{\max} = -47.2$ N/mm² for $r = 65$ mm).

Fig. 5 shows the distributions of vertical stresses in the same way, but for an eccentric introduction of the wheel load. The eccentric applied load was achieved in the FE-model with an additional torsion moment $M_T = F_z \cdot k/4$ ($k = 25$ mm for rail type A 100) on the top of the rail (see chapter 2.1). The vertical stresses in the transverse stiffeners are now always at the load facing side (see Fig. 5a). The highest stresses occur for the circular cut-outs (v2) independent of their size ($\sigma_{\max} = -$

168.7 N/mm²). For details 1 and 2 the eccentric load introduction leads to a completely different behaviour of the stresses in the web plate. In Fig. 5b the stresses on the load facing side of the web plate are plotted with the solid lines and in dashed lines on the load averted side. On the top edge of the web there is a clear additional bending which manifests by higher compression stresses at the load facing edge ($\sigma_{\max} = -117.4$ N/mm²) and nearly no stresses at the load averted edge of the web. The stresses on the horizon of detail 2 are significantly smaller than for detail 1 and the maximum value of $\sigma_{\max} = -73.0$ N/mm² is on the load averted edge of the web. Since the transverse bending of the web plate at the lower end of the cut out is reversed, it has a beneficial effect on the intention of the vertical stresses.

Fig. 5. Distribution of vertical stresses σ_z , a) in the transverse stiffener; b) in the web of the crane girder in longitudinal direction for detail 1 and 2, for FE models 1 to 5 and an applied eccentric wheel load of $F_z = 250$ kN, $e = 25$ mm

3.2 Influence of different rail types

Fig. 6 shows the maximum value of the vertical compression stresses in the web plate at the horizon of detail 1 (first diagram), detail 2 (second diagram) and at detail 3 in the transverse stiffener (third diagram).

The geometry of the crane runway girder and the shape of the cut-out (v2, $r = 65$ mm) is always the same, only the rail type changes. The maximum value of stresses directly under the load introduction are plotted for a concentric load introduction (black lines) as well as for an eccentric load introduction (red and blue lines).

For the stresses at details 1 and 2 larger rails lead to a significant reduction of the maximum stresses for concentric as well as for eccentric load introduction. For detail 1 the largest stresses occur, as expected, at the load facing edge of the web with eccentric load introduction (red line is the highest). The results of detail 2 shows again the benefits of the reversed bending. The magnitude of bending stresses is significantly lower than for detail 1 (distance between red and blue line) and the load averted side has the highest compression stresses (blue line is on top).

For detail 3 there is no influence of the rail type with concentric load introduction. In the case of eccentric load application, the stresses in the transverse stiffener increase with the larger rail types. Since the larger rail types are more compact, they can distribute the load in transverse direction and more of the load is introduced in the load facing transverse stiffener.

Fig. 6. Maximum vertical stresses at detail 1, 2 and 3 for different rail types – comparison of FE-models 4, 18, 23 and 24, with cut-out variant v2 and for an applied wheel load of $F_z = 250$ kN

3.3 Influence of crane runway girder's geometry

Within the parametric study different geometries of crane runway girders were investigated. Fig. 7 shows the maximum compression stresses at details 1, 2 and 3 for different flange thickness values t_f of the crane runway girder ($h_w = 2000$ mm, $t_w = 15$ mm, $t_s = 10$ mm, rail A 100, cut-out variant v2).

Fig. 7. Maximum vertical stresses at detail 1, 2 and 3 for crane runway girders flanges of different thickness t_f – comparison of FE-models 4, 7, 8 and 9 for an applied wheel load of $F_z = 250$ kN

In Fig. 7 the maximum compression stresses due to a concentric applied load decrease with an increase of the flange thickness for all three details. Thicker flanges allow for a better load distributing behaviour in longitudinal direction of the crane runway girder. For eccentric applied load also the transverse bending component in the web at detail 1 and 2 is significantly reduced with thicker flanges as well as the stresses in the load facing transverse stiffener (detail 3).

3.4 Influence of the thickness of the transverse stiffeners

Fig. 8. Maximum vertical stresses at detail 1, 2 and 3 for transverse stiffeners of different thickness – comparison of FE-models 4, 13 and 14 for an applied wheel load of $F_z = 250$ kN

The Influence of the thickness of the transverse stiffeners t_s on the maximum vertical stresses is shown in *Fig. 8*, keeping all the other dimensions constant ($h_w = 2000$ mm, $t_w = 15$ mm, $t_f = 20$ mm, rail A 100, cut-out variant v2).

No influence is visible for detail 1, neither for concentric nor for eccentric load introduction. For detail 2 a small increase in the maximum compression stresses with thicker transverse stiffeners can be shown. The compression stresses at detail 3 decrease with an increase of thickness of the transverse stiffeners, but only for eccentric loads.

4 IMPACT ON THE FATIGUE ASSESSMENT

prEN 1993-6 (1) allows for calculating the local stresses at detail 1 between two transverse stiffeners. The actual stresses near the stiffeners cannot be calculated based on the regulations in the code. To show the influence of the fatigue assessment of detail 1 at the position of a transverse stiffener and the additional constructional details 2 and 3 the utilization factor of the fatigue verification is calculated for each detail in relation to the fatigue design of detail 1 without transverse stiffener. The classification of the fatigue resistance of details 1 to 3 is shown in *Table 2* according to prEN 1993-1-9 (2).

Table 2. classification of the fatigue resistance for detail 1, 2 and 3 according to prEN 1993-1-9

Constructional detail	description	Fatigue resistance $\Delta\sigma_c$
1	Welded connection between top flange and web with full penetration weld (crack initiation in the web at the weld toe)	100
2	Welded connection between transverse stiffener with cut out and crane girders web with fillet weld (crack initiation in the web at the weld toe)	63
3	Welded connection between transverse stiffener and crane girders top flange with fillet weld (crack initiation in weld root)	50

The utilization factor for the fatigue design according to EN 1993-1-9 for an equivalent stress range $\Delta\sigma_z$ is calculated with *Eq. (2)*.

$$\frac{\gamma_{F,f} \Delta\sigma_z}{\Delta\sigma_c / \gamma_{M,f}} \leq 1,0 \quad (2)$$

As reference the utilization factor for the fatigue design at detail 1 between two transverse stiffeners is taken. The reference values of the maximum stresses at the top edge of the crane girders web in between two transverse stiffeners, at position $x = 0.5a$, with $a/h_w = 1,0$, where a is the distance between the transverse stiffeners and h_w is the web height (see *Fig. 2*) are taken from FE-calculations which have been carried out with similar cross sections of crane runway girders in (9). The reference stresses between two transverse stiffeners $\Delta\sigma_{z,0}$ is compared with the maximum stresses $\Delta\sigma_{z,1}$, $\Delta\sigma_{z,2}$ and $\Delta\sigma_{z,3}$ at details 1, 2 and 3 related to their fatigue resistance according to *Table 2* lead to the ratio η of the fatigue verification.

$$\eta = \frac{\Delta\sigma_{z,i} / \Delta\sigma_{c,i}}{\Delta\sigma_{z,0} / \Delta\sigma_{c,0}} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 9 illustrate these normalized utilization factors η of details 1 to 3 related to the utilization of detail 1 between two transverse stiffeners. Values $\eta < 1,0$ indicates that no additional fatigue verification at the transverse stiffener is necessary. The evaluation of detail 1 in *Fig. 9a* shows that there is no significant difference between the verification of detail 1 with or without transverse stiffener. If there is a cut-out in the transverse stiffener (assumed in all studied cases), the magnitudes of the vertical stresses are approximately of the same size.

Fig. 9. Factors η_i – utilization factor for the fatigue verification of a) detail 1, b) detail 2 and c) detail 3 related to the fatigue utilization factor of detail 1 between two transverse stiffeners

The evaluation of the fatigue verification of detail 2 is shown in Fig. 9b. It can be shown that the fatigue design of detail 2 becomes decisive related to the design of detail 1 without transverse stiffeners. The magnitude of the vertical stresses at the lower end of the cut-out is in the same range as on the top edge of the web plate, but the fatigue resistance is much smaller. For eccentric load introduction the beneficial effect of the reversed bending effect is manifested in smaller utilization factors.

The related utilization factors for detail 3 are much higher than 1.0. Since the low fatigue resistance of $\Delta\sigma_{c,3} = 50$ MPa is assumed for fillet welds at this detail, which includes crack initiation at the weld root, the fatigue design of this detail becomes crucial. But also for a full penetration butt weld this constructional detail is still relevant.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Within this paper the local vertical stresses at the critical points (details 1 to 3 – see Fig. 1b) of the connections of transverse stiffeners in crane runway girders were determined in a numerical parameter study. The influence of different cross sections of crane runway girders, crane rail types and the geometry of transverse stiffeners have been investigated. The impact on the fatigue verification was shown related to the fatigue design of the welded connection between the crane

girders web and flange at positions without transverse stiffeners. The following insights were obtained:

- For detail 1 at the top of the girders web it can be shown that there is no significant difference between the evaluation for load introduction between transverse stiffeners and directly above a transverse stiffener (see *Fig. 1a*). The stresses are in the same range because the load relief of the stiffener is very low. However, it can be said that for detail 1 the fatigue verification based on Eurocode (1, 2) is covered.
- For detail 2, in the web plate at the cut-out, the beneficial behaviour of the transverse bending in the web plate provides that there is no higher fatigue utilization for an eccentric load introduction. Since this effect depends on the magnitude of the eccentricity and on the shape of the cut-out it is not clear whether this is the case for all practical cases. For a concentric load introduction, it can be shown that detail 2 gets decisive for the fatigue verification related to detail 1. Since the stresses at detail 2 are not reduced that much (depends on the elongation of the cut-out), but the fatigue resistance is smaller, the fatigue utilization becomes higher (maximum increase for equal stresses $100/63 = 1.59$).
- The results for detail 3, at the transverse stiffener, shows that there might be a problem with the fatigue assessment of this detail if the transverse stiffeners are welded to the top flange with fillet welds only. The utilization factors become up to 2 to 4 times higher than for detail 1. This leads also to problems with full penetration butt welds. However, this detail should be modified in a way that the transverse stiffener is not welded directly to the top flange (e.g. with bolted end plate).

The results within this paper clearly show that more investigations and laboratory test should be carried out to allow for a deeper understanding of the complex stress fields near transverse stiffeners. For an accurate evaluation design rules for determining the stresses at the details 1, 2 and 3 are necessary. As beneficial solution for detail 2 an elongation of the cut-out can reduce the stresses and lead to an improvement of the fatigue design. For detail 3 bolted connections between transverse stiffeners and top flange can avoid the worse constructional detail in this connection.

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